

I spoke a few days ago to David Whitehouse and he told me that he had understood from David Stronach that I had been imprisoned in Bushehr and only released after representations in Teheran!!! There must have been a considerable misunderstanding somewhere, and I wish to correct this story because I believe it seriously distorts the Iranian attitude towards British research on the Gulf. To give details of what did happen I enclose a copy of a report I submitted to David Stronach and on my own volition gave the Iranian Archaeological Service in July 1971 together with a second report bringing the matter up to date.

I wish to emphasise the following points arising from these reports:

- a) The Bushehr Peninsula is unlike anywhere else on the Persian Gulf coast because of the concentration there of military installations. Before surveying there, with the collaboration of the local representative of the Iranian Ministry of Culture and Arts I obtained written permission and a military guide from the Air Force Officer in charge of the Peninsula.
- b) I was never arrested in Bushehr. I was for less than one hour questioned by the Navy on my bonafides. When they had checked my papers and seen the local representative of Arts and Culture they were most apologetic and blamed the fact that I had been stopped on interservice rivalry.

They raised no objection to my continuing survey at Bushehr, although I chose not to. They did however take my film to check that there were no photos of their installations.

- c) Some time after this the Iranian Archaeological Service was asked by the State Security Organisation for details about myself, so the Archaeological Service wrote to David Stronach requesting information. They were embarrassed because neither they nor the Institute had many details about myself (The Institute had perhaps lost a curriculum vitae handed to the Director in April 1970). I visited Teheran and gave the Archaeological Service a curriculum vitae. No other information was required. The Iranian Archaeological Service did not consider the matter serious enough to call me before the Director General nor to withdraw my permit which they could have done if there was any suspicion at all about my intentions. They did however, emphasising that it was their own decision and for my protection tell me not to survey this year on the Persian Gulf coast North of ~~Bandar~~ Bandar Abbas, but only to work in the Minab area. David Stronach tells me that in mid August he was advised that I should not survey on the coast at all. This information was never communicated by the Archaeological Service to me and although I made a trip to Teheran to find out David Stronach did not tell me until late October !
- d) The British Embassy was to the best of my knowledge never involved although David Stronach very wisely informed them of the position. (I presume he believed I had been in jail.)
- e) I did not, on the specific advice of David Stronach write to you about this when I was in Iran.

I hope that this in conjunction with the enclosed reports clarifies any misunderstandings of the position.. I do not wish to justify all my own actions, but I do wish to make it clear that Iranian sensitivities over the Gulf are not nearly as great as might have been supposed. My questioning in Bushehr was certainly a much smaller incident than David Whitehouse believed before speaking to me.

I am sure that you have seen that the Iranians through British mediation made a peaceable agreement with Sharja over the occupation of the Island of Abu Musa, and that only the two Tumbs were taken by force from the